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Dichotomy of the 'Clip Thinking' Phenomenon

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Abstract

The paper describes the phenomenon of '*clip thinking*' from interdisciplinary perspective. Clip thinking is regarded as a process of reflecting a multitude of various properties of objects, without taking into account the relationships between them, characterized by fragmented information flow, illogicality, heterogeneity of incoming information, high speed of switching between fragments of information as well as the lack of a holistic perception of the surrounding world.

The phenomenon of clip thinking is essentially synonymous with the concept of '*cognitive style*'. The '*differential / integral*' cognitive styles are associated with individual features of students' digestion of the teaching material. Students with integral type of cognitive style tend to rely on educational technologies built on the principle of transition from abstract to concrete, whereas students with differential type of cognitive style are inclined to learn from a specific focus to a general one.

Within the context of clip thinking, we need to:

- revise the content of the learning material;
- organize information in the form of clips;
- modify the format of information presentation ;
- apply bright, clear and visual presentations with clear, imaginative and catchy formulations.

The application of common teaching methods together with e-learning technologies will increase the efficiency of the learning process as well as significantly enhance students' professional training.

Key words: Clip, Clip thinking, Zapping, Blip culture, Cognitive style.

1. Introduction

The increased role of knowledge, information and information technologies has led to a new stage of development of the modern society. Information technologies are widely used in everyday life, production, institutions, and the education system as a whole. The global information space provides effective interaction of people, satisfaction of their needs in information products and services, as well as access to the world resources.

Global informatization is changing man's mental activity. Thus, under the influence of television, computer games, the Internet and even modern literature, most representatives of the younger generation are forming a special type of thinking – 'clip thinking'.

The analysis of interdisciplinary works in philosophy, cultural studies and psychology devoted to the phenomenon of clip thinking, has revealed the contradiction associated with the essence of orthodox educational paradigm, which responds quite slowly to the rapid changes in modern society, where information is the main resource. As a result, there is a clear discrepancy between updated internal expectations of individuals with clip consciousness and a measured rhythm and stable character of the educational foundations.

2. Theoretical Fundamentals

The aim of the paper is to conduct an interdisciplinary analysis of clip thinking. The word *clip* often refers to the principles of constructing music videos, or music clips, where the video consists of loosely linked images. This is an underlying principle of a cliché worldview, when a person perceives the world as a series of almost unconnected parts, facts or events. Clip thinking hinders analytical abilities, since the images that remain in thoughts only for a short period of time, almost immediately disappear being replaced by the new ones (Semenovskikh, 2002).

The media are excessively manipulating the word 'clip' in the context of thinking, although the term 'clip thinking' initially emerged in philosophical and psychological literature in the late 1990s to denote the peculiarity of a person to perceive the world through a bright short message embodied in the form of either a video clip (hence the name) or television news (Azarenok, 2009).

Originally, it was the media rather than the World Wide Web that developed a universal format for presenting information through the so-called sequence of current clips. In this case, a clip is a short set of abstracts submitted without defining the context, since

the objective reality itself serves as the context of the clip due to its relevance. Thus, a person is free to perceive and interpret the clip because it is immersed in this very reality. In fact, not everything is as beautiful as it looks at first glance, since in view of the fragmented nature of the information flow and the spacing of related events over time, the brain simply cannot comprehend the connection between them. Consequently, the clip turns into information noise. However, the message of the clip is retained in the person's perception, thereby reading news fosters an illusion of being aware of the processes taking place in the world, while, in effect, it results in a set of discrete facts that are almost impossible to link or associate with the general chain of events. The format of the media forces the brain to make a fundamental comprehension mistake, i.e. the events are considered to be connected if they have a temporary affinity, rather than a factual one. It is therefore no wonder that the clip thinking emerged as a response to the increased amount of information.

According to McLuhan's theory of civilization (McLuhan, 1988), at the present stage of its development the society is being transformed into an e-society or a global village, whereby the Internet and social media are creating a multidimensional perception of the world. The development of electronic means of communication is taking back human thinking to the pre-text era, where the linear sequence of signs ceases to serve as a cultural base.

The phenomenon of *clip culture* was first noted by A. Toffler, an American futurist (Toffler, 1984), who viewed this concept as a component of the general information culture, that forms such a unique form of perception as 'zapping', when non-stop switching of TV channels creates a new image, consisting of scraps of information or debris of impressions. This image requires no imagination or reflection; the information is constantly updated, since everything seen in the news report without a temporary gap tends to lose its meaning or become obsolete. Furthermore, Toffler introduced the term 'blip', i.e. mosaic perceptions of the world that arise from audiovisual electronic information in terms of its demassification. Hence, those who prefer logical harmony and integrity of the mass media broadcast struggle to comprehend the chaos of blip-cultural information.

Girenok (Girenok, 2002) was the first to use the term *clip thinking* in Russian literature, believing that conceptual thinking ceased to play an important role in the modern world, whereby linear, binary thinking is being replaced with a nonlinear one. The European culture is built on a system of evidence, whereas the Russian culture with its Byzantine roots is grounded on the system of visualization. Therefore, Russians have evolved, perhaps following John of Damascus, towards the perception of images, which is intrinsically related to clip thinking.

According to Feldman (Feldman), clip thinking is a conditioned thinking, which allows a person to process fixed-length content rather than semiotic structures of arbitrary complexity. This is particularly visible in a person who is incapable of concentrating on any information for long periods to subsequently provide its critical analysis.

Clip thinking, as defined by Frumkin (Frumkin, 2010), is a vector of the development of a new level of person's relation with information, characterized by the ability to

quickly switch between disjointed semantic fragments, as well as our inability to perceive a long linear sequence of homogeneous information.

Frumkin identified five factors that contributed to the phenomenon of 'clip thinking':

- accelerated pace of life and the subsequent increase in the volume of the information flow unduly burdensome to select, filter out and differentiate between the essential and the non-essential;
- systematically updated information;
- increased diversity of incoming information;
- extended multi-tasking;
- enhanced democracy and an on-going dialogue at different levels of the social system.

The main problem with clip thinking is the lack of context, which elucidates the significance of separate fragments in a meaningful verbal or written speech (Frumkin, 2010). When you perceive any meaningful text, a certain context is formed as a set of statements and assumptions that have already been considered within the scope of the topic in question both in the existing context and in the context of your own knowledge and expertise. The longer the text is, the more complex its context is, and therefore the easier it is for us to understand the semantic relations between phenomena, which, in fact, exist before our eyes, namely in a context.

Clip thinking impedes a clear understanding of the context, and therefore, a clip leaves no traces in semantically related phenomena. Although a clip is a form of information representation, its interpretation could be particularly problematic, for instance, for a person who is indifferent to politics and therefore unable to understand the causes and consequences of the political events, since he fails to see any connection between the isolated facts. In contrast, a politically conscious person relies on the context that correlates the clips to provide a unified view of the political situation (Bryksin, 2012).

The relation between experience and behavior was central to Carl Roger's *Phenomenological Theory of Personality*. Rogers believed that people's behavior is influenced by their current perceptions and interpretation. In other words, their subjective experience determines the behavior that cannot be understood without subjective interpretation of the events.

Furthermore, Carl Rogers was the proponent of a holistic approach to personality that suggests that the person is regarded as a whole, and this unity cannot be reduced to the constituent elements of his personality.

The transition from a holistic approach to clip thinking is the transition from holism to elementalism. This indicates a fragmentation and contradiction in thinking. In his article 'Is Google making us stupid?' Nicholas Carr (Carr, 2001) wrote: "Over the past few years I've had an uncomfortable sense that someone, or something, has been tinkering with my brain, remapping the neural circuitry, reprogramming the memory. My mind isn't going—so far as I can tell—but it's changing. I'm not thinking the way I used to think. I can feel it most strongly when I'm reading. Immersing myself in a

book or a lengthy article used to be easy. My mind would get caught up in the narrative or the turns of the argument, and I'd spend hours strolling through long stretches of prose. That's rarely the case anymore. Now my concentration often starts to drift after two or three pages. I get fidgety, lose the thread, and begin looking for something else to do. I feel as if I'm always dragging my wayward brain back to the text. The deep reading that used to come naturally has become a struggle”.

One of the peculiarities of clip thinking is the development of some cognitive skills at the expense of others. In his book 'Me, MySpace, and I: Parenting the Net Generation' Larry D. Rosen, an American psychologist, notes that the strength of the Internet Generation, brought up in the era of internet-based communication technologies, demonstrate a higher propensity for multitasking, for instance, presentday children can do homework while simultaneously listening to music, chatting, editing pictures or surfing the Internet. However multitasking leads to a lack of concentration and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). Moreover, Net Geners prefer visual symbols to logic.

Since the consciousness of a modern man is experiencing unprecedented influx of chaotic and heterogeneous information that clogs the channels of perception with excessive, unwanted data, clip thinking acts as a protective shield against information overload (Golovin, 1998). Thus, clip thinking proves to serve as a kind of protection against information overload in modern society, particularly when a person needs to digest diverse information. Clip thinking is creating a new information management tool; therefore, network communications are as important for a modern man as the ordinary ones.

Clip thinking can be defined as the process that allows humans to make sense of the world they experience and of various properties of multiple objects, characterized by a lack of a holistic perception of illogical flow of heterogeneous information and rapid switching between its fragments, without analyzing their connections. In our opinion, the main characteristics of clip thinking are as follows: concrete thinking, fragmentation (lack of a holistic perception), focus on less general concepts, illogicality and lability.

3. Students' Clip Thinking: Psycho-Didactic Aspects

Recently, among educators and psychologists a stable opinion has emerged that nowadays young people perceive the world around them too superficially. Thus, Vronsky (Vronsky, 2012) believes that the entire system of young men's values and ideals is too monotonous and is based solely on the information flow that literally 'pours' in on them from television screens and the Internet. The ability to formulate an idea in a clear and comprehensible way to convey its meaning has become a rarity. Equally, the inability of modern students to listen carefully and write down the conclusions of the lecture in a coherent way has come under increasing criticism from professors.

This is due to the fact that today the information space as the total result of human semantic activities involves extensive written and audiovisual communication. On the one hand, excessive information environment entails the need for the person to rapidly assimilate as much information as possible; on the other hand, it evokes qualitative changes in the format of the information itself. There is a steady tendency to represent information in a fragmented manner with a focus on its quantity, rather than quality. These changes determined the emergence of such a phenomenon as 'clip thinking' and the subsequent need to redesign the approach to teaching young people.

Can clip thinking contribute to the effective assimilation of information in the learning process? There is no unambiguous answer to the above question. The application of clip thinking in education allows a person to memorize huge amounts of information without perceiving its content, in other words, to quickly memorize a set of words, phrases or numbers in a certain sequence on the basis of some images that correspond to the information to be memorized (Semenovskikh, 2002).

Such methods are suitable, for instance, for studying foreign languages, where a foreign word can correspond to some image of a word from the native language. However, in physics, it will result in memorization of some terms, rules, definitions or formulas, therefore the understanding of physical processes will be lost.

The language of images and gestures is much older than the language of symbols; therefore, it is easier for a man to perceive information in the form of images rather than letters, numbers, formulas, etc. A lecture is still regarded as a classical (traditional) form of organization of higher education. The above-mentioned system of images proves to be the most efficient way of memorizing the learning material from a more focused approach to the lecture's content and duration with an emphasis on modern multimedia technologies.

Current articles examine the rules for developing electronic textbooks that, unlike paper versions, should contain separate sections on specific topics, including animation, especially in the study of physical foundations of various processes. The formation of images in educational process using modern computer technologies is unlikely to pose a serious challenge. These images can be represented in the form of slides or short animated pictures, i.e. clips. It is important to keep in mind, though, that students should associate the small-scale sequence of clips with quite definite images, rather than abstract content. The proposed method of presenting information in the form of a clip allows us to merely memorize it, without consciously absorbing it (Pudalov, 2011).

Furthermore, a measure of overlap exists between clip thinking per se and the cognitive style; therefore, it is necessary to take into account the recommendations for the learning process with regard to students' cognitive style. A complex approach to learning with an emphasis on clip and cognitive thinking is described in the work of Berulava (Berulava, 2001), that presents a set of methodological recommendations for helping students not only master the material, but also realize their full potential.

In her study, Berulava proves that clip thinking and the differential / integral cognitive style both relate to specific perception and assimilation of learning material. Thus, students with integral type of cognitive style tend to rely on educational technologies

built on the principle of transition from abstract to concrete through discussions, whereas students with differential type of cognitive style are inclined to learn from a specific focus to a general one through logical and formalized perception of the material, either on the basis of their integral knowledge, or consistent cognition.

In general, we have every reason to believe that modern educators and psychologists should integrate essential features of clip thinking in learning environment, including students' educational and extra-curricular activities. It is highly advisable to revise the content of the learning material with an emphasis on students' individual psychological characteristics. The format of information should be modified and translated into the form of clips, i.e. bright, clear and visual presentations with understandable, imaginative and memorable formulations. The challenge is to create ad hoc films or video clips with illustrative examples, experiments, etc.

Advanced pedagogical tools combined with e-learning technologies will increase the efficiency of the learning process and significantly improve the students' professional training.

4. Conclusions

The main findings of the interdisciplinary analysis of the research on clip thinking are as follows:

- clip thinking can be defined as the process that allows humans to make sense of the world they experience and of various properties of multiple objects, characterized by a lack of a holistic perception of illogical flow of heterogeneous information and rapid switching between its fragments, without analyzing their connections;
- a measure of overlap exists between clip thinking per se and the cognitive style;
- the students' differential / integral cognitive style is associated with individual features of their perception of the learning material, which should be presented in short semantic fragments with regard to their psychological characteristics.

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